

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Integration and adoption roadmap of
assessment tools**

Work Package 2 - Deliverable 2.2

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Executive Summary

The Specialisation Tool, co-developed by the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF) and the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS), builds on the foundations of the CETAF Registry and is structured around a suite of thematic data collection forms, including institutions, collections, digitisation, facilities, expertise, research, exhibitions, and training. The tool enables institutions to contribute and update data through standardised Google Forms linked to a Django-based back-end system, which stores the information in a PostgreSQL database. This technical architecture allows for automatic data harvesting, transformation, and export via an API, and supports interoperability with key DiSSCo services such as the European Loans and Visits System and the Collection Digitisation Dashboard.

Key achievements include the successful deployment of a CETAF API, which supports data exchange using standards like Latimer Core, and the development of a database model that supports versioning and change tracking. The project confirmed the viability and strategic advantage of using open-source technologies (PostgreSQL, Django, Grafana), which allow rapid development and support long-term sustainability.

To enhance accessibility and support decision-making, data from the tool can be visualised through interactive dashboards. While initial data collection still relies on Google-based services, the core infrastructure is independent and can evolve toward full open-source implementation, reducing reliance on non-EU providers and aligning more closely with GDPR and FAIR principles.

The Specialisation Tool is essential for identifying Centres of Excellence within the DiSSCo network and for supporting evidence-based management, collaboration, and service delivery. It empowers a wide range of users, from institutional managers and policy makers to curators and researchers, by offering a comprehensive, dynamic overview of DiSSCo's distributed capacities. As a central component of DiSSCo's emerging service ecosystem, the tool strengthens community engagement, enhances data visibility, and contributes directly to the long-term success and sustainability of the infrastructure.

Keywords

DiSSCo RI; Specialisation Plan; Natural Science Collections; Strategy; Self-Assessment

List of abbreviations

API - Application Programming Interface
CA - Consortium Agreement
CEAB - Centro de Estudios Avanzados de Blanes
CDD - Collection Digitisation Dashboard
CETAF - Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities
CoEs - Centres of Excellence
CSIC - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
CSO - Coordination and Support Office
CT - Computed Tomography
D - Deliverable
DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project
ELViS - European Loans and Visits System
ERIC - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
GA - Grant Agreement
GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation
GRSciColl - Global Registry of Scientific Collections
ISO - International Standards Organisation
MBG - Meise Botanic Garden
MfN- Museum für Naturkunde
MIDS - Multifunctional Information Distribution System
MNHN -Museum National d’Histoire Naturelles
MS - Milestone
NNs - National Nodes
NSCs - Natural Science Collections
ORCID ID - Open Researcher and Contributor ID
SPOC - Single Person Of Contact
RBINS - Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
RI - Research Infrastructure
RMCA - Royal Museum for Central Africa
RO - Research Output
ROR - Research Organization Registry
T - Task

TETTRIs - Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research and Innovations
WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo) (<https://www.dissco.eu/>) is a pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI) that aims to transform and unify natural science collections (NSCs) into one integrated digital resource. DiSSCo is currently transitioning into a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), uniting institutions, museums, and botanical gardens across 23 countries to digitise and aggregate 1.5 billion specimens into a single European digital collection. This vast digital repository is intended to support researchers, policymakers, educators, and the public by ensuring seamless access to natural science collections.

A crucial element in DiSSCo's maturation is the collaboration between RBINS and CETAF, initiated under DiSSCo Prepare, a former phase of DiSSCo (Koureas et al. 2023), on the development of a Specialisation Plan, hereafter referred as Specialisation Tool, a prototype tool platform allowing the gathering, categorising, storage and analysis of NSCs related information. The prototype shall be implemented at the European RI for the integration of NSCs related data from more than 1000 institutions in perspective. As such, the Specialisation Tool is fundamentally strategic for DiSSCo RI, as it allows to map the network of participating institutions into DiSSCo, to discover and to provide institution and NSCs data to the DiSSCo RI infrastructure, and eventually to highlight strengths and expertises, identify gaps and take strategic decisions to deploy the capacities of DiSSCo. In turns, the tool is also crucial for the identification of Centres of Excellence (CoEs) – institutions or consortia recognised for their expertise in digitisation, preservation, exploitation and management of natural science collections. These CoEs play a pivotal role in advancing high-quality digitisation, data conservation, and best practices across DiSSCo's network.

This deliverable presents the concept and the role of the Specialisation Tool, its technical aspects, including the data collection workflow, and an exploitation roadmap, including linkage with other DiSSCo Services and the user engagement strategy. The document is a key deliverable under DiSSCo Transition Work Package 2 (WP2), Task 2.2 (T2.2): “Identify means to sustainably collect, aggregate, and analyse information from National Nodes (NNs).” The objective of T2.2 was to establish sustainable methods for collecting, aggregating, and analysing information from DiSSCo National Nodes to enhance participation in the Research Infrastructure. This involved:

- Expanding data collected in previous DiSSCo-related projects to develop well-grounded tools.
- Structuring community contributions into meaningful dashboards.
- Identifying priority areas for informed decision making.
- Strengthening pathways for institutions to contribute to DiSSCo objectives.

The task supports the usability of the Specialisation Tool (linked to the CETAF Registry of Collections), a key mechanism initiated during the DiSSCo Preparatory Phase. The document will not be discussing the Digital Maturity Self-Assessment Tool nor the Policy

Compliance Tools specifically as these mechanisms are not part of the Specialisation Tool and thus out of the scope of this deliverable.

By establishing sustainable data collection methods and reinforcing strategic partnerships, this effort aims to enhance the long-term success of DiSSCo as an integrated, standardised, and globally recognised research infrastructure.

1.2. Scope

Coverage and focus

This roadmap focuses on the design, implementation, maintenance and sustainability of the CETAF/DiSSCo Specialisation Tool. This tool will serve as an authoritative data source for:

- Collecting high-level institutional data, including collection scope and size, digitisation capacity, facilities, organisational structure, research expertise, and training programs.
- Providing data to DiSSCo services, such as the European Loans and Visits System ([ELViS](#)) and the Collection Digitisation Dashboard (CDD).
- Providing a user-friendly interface for viewing and analysing data, that will be integrated into the CETAF website to support strategic decision making, including: Identifying Centres of Excellence (CoEs), facilitating research collaborations, supporting policy development and national/international strategic management.

The intended audience of this roadmap is for maintainers of the CETAF/DiSSCo Specialisation Tool, which will be CETAF in collaboration of RBINS & the Royal Museum for Central Africa (RMCA), DiSSCo service providers, DiSSCo members, as well as all potential users of the tool.

Development history

The CETAF DiSSCo Specialisation Tool was developed based on the CETAF Registry of collections, which aims to provide reliable and structured high-level data on CETAF and DiSSCo Institutions including their institution staff and structure, collections, facilities, exhibitions (just CETAF), training, and research focus. The Registry is a replacement of the CETAF passports, which was a part of the old CETAF website and contained unstructured and limited institutional data.

Development milestones

2018/19: Initial partnership with RBINS to replace CETAF Passports, which contained only basic institutional data (Postal address, director names, research focus, expertise and collection size).

2019/20: Development of the CETAF Registry as an authoritative data source for DiSSCo. The CETAF registry was initially designed as a centralised platform based on Plone - that sat separately from the CETAF website. It was designed to streamline the process of CETAF and DiSSCo institutions providing high-level information about their organisational structure, Collection scope and size, facilities and research expertise and training

programmes. The idea was that people could add their information directly to their relevant institutions by logging onto the Plone system at any time rather than having to wait for CETAF to send around an excel spreadsheet like with the CETAF passports.

2020 - 2023: During the DiSSCo Prepare Project, the CETAF Registry tool was expanded to support the DiSSCo Specialisation Tool. This initiative led to the conceptualisation of the CETAF DiSSCo Specialisation Tool, as outlined in this deliverable report.

2023 - 2024: The Plone system was abandoned due to concerns over potential system overload when multiple users accessed it simultaneously. Additionally, Plone was considered too complex for users to navigate and input data efficiently. As a result, a new system based on Google Forms was introduced, leveraging the familiarity of users with the Google ecosystem to enhance accessibility and ease of use. A Django backend, with its own database storing data in JSON format, has been developed and linked to an REST API.

2024 - 2025: During the current DiSSCo Transition Project, the platform was developed and tested with several institutions. The google forms were enriched with google sheets for data integration. The backend was also reworked to fit with the requirements of the DiSSCo services. Concurrently, the project [BE.DiSSCo-Fed](#) got funded by the Belgian federal government to explore, define, and develop the tool on the base of the DiSSCo Prepare prototype to collect data among Belgian Institutions and provide a prototype use case for using the tool beyond Belgium across the whole DiSSCo RI network and to facilitate the interconnection with GRSciColl.

2025: Working on the Django back-end, finalisation of the Google forms and of their Python parser, reworking of the part of the Zope website serving as entry point to the material for the specialisation platform. Meetings with [ELViS](#) and [GRSciColl](#) (registry of Natural Sciences History and collections managed by GBIF) to 1) agree on a common data structure using [Latimer Core](#) terms, and taking the [MIDS](#) (*Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen*) fields into account, 2) connect the specialisation API with other services and 3) define the cycles for data updates.

2. Technical components

This section presents the technical components of the CETAF DiSSCo Specialisation Tool (Figure 1).

CETAF/DiSSCo specialisation

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Choose one of the topic to access the menu

Figure 1: Topics covered by the Specialisation Tool.

The Specialisation Tool aims to collect information among DiSSCo organisations about the structures, collection facilities, research facilities, research, expertise and training.

Institution data are stored in JSON (PostgreSQL JSONB, which is unordered) format, allowing dynamic adaptation of the database in case of change in schema

4. `cetaf_api_collections_normalised` like for institutions, this table is created only once and contains the identifiers of the institutions. It is created when an institution first appears in the survey data. Normalising the collections is needed to link to institutions. This table features a foreign key to the normalised institutions
5. `cetaf_api_collections` his table contains the collections data along with:
 - a. the list of the different identifiers (CETAF/ROR/WikiData, GRSciColl) resolvable through the URL
 - b. a link to the child collections (2nd level sub-collections)
 - c. a link to the parent collections
 - d. A link to the sister or parent institution
 - e. A link to the normalised institution

Institution data are stored in JSON format, allowing dynamic adaptation of the database in case of change in schema. Currently the geographical coverage, MIDS and storage are harvested.

```

"mail": "olavi.kurina@emu.ee",
"orcid": {
  "id": "0000-0002-4858-4629",
  "data": {
    "name": {
      "given_name": "Olavi",
      "family_name": "Kurina"
    },
    "emails": [],
    "keywords": [
      "Taxonomy, Systematics, Diversity, Distribution, Diptera, Sciaroidea"
    ],
    "affiliation": {
      "role": [
        "research assistant",
        "researcher",
        "Head of department",
        "senior researcher",
        "Professor of Systematic Entomology"
      ],
      "department": [
        "Zoology",
        "Institute of Zoology and Hydrobiology",
        "Zoological department",
        "Department of Zoology",
        "Chair of Biodiversity and Nature Tourism"
      ]
    },
    "last_modification": "2025-02-05 16:54:04"
  },
  "source": "orcid"
}

```

Figure 6: Collector data filled with ORCID: the curator just provided its ORCID number, names, affiliations and keywords are fetched from ORCID JSON API

During harvesting, the Django API can connect external APIs to enrich data, avoiding collections managers and curators filling the survey to provide data he already provided to other networks. Currently ORCID (for personnel data) and GRSciColl (for institutions and collections) are covered.

Output data can also be converted into other schemas and vocabularies, e.g. Latimer Core for interoperability with ELViS and GRSciColl (see below). The Django code contains an internal parser, using a syntax similar to XSLT, for JSON data and Python dictionary, to convert output data to alternative structures. The idea is to have these transformations defined in variables, and normalised path, rather than hardcoded.

The Django code also pushes the data from the PostgreSQL database to ElasticSearch indexes, in order to send data to the existing search engine of the CETAF website (<https://cetaf.org/explore/>).

This is done via a Python bash command. The Python code to:

1. fetch data from sheet and spreadsheet in the Google cloud
2. connect external APIs,
3. transform JSON output data into different schemas
4. push data to ElasticSearch

API parser inherits from interfaces (in the object oriented sense) to stabilise the code syntax in a modular way and make it easier to expand and adapt.

Data is handled internally as Pandas DataFrame, storing and transforming data (including computation of statistics, summing subcollection data into the parent collection) from the Google Cloud sheets. Connection to Google cloud to get the sheets is made via OAuth libraries (“pydrive”, “googleapiclient” and “google.oauth2” Python libraries to explore data, “pygsheets” to link to Pandas).

```
JSON_TRANSFORMS={
  "elvis_ltc":{
    "src":[
      "/data/@/{identifier:$1}",
      "/data/@/parent_institution_list_identifiers/@/{type:$7, value:$8}",
      "/data/@/data/data_list/@/data/collection_data/storage/$5/object_quantity/detail/{$4:$6}",
      "/data/@/data/data_list/@/data/collection_data/geospatial_coverage/country_list/$2/$3/{$4:Yes}",
      "/data/@/data/data_list/@/data/main_metadata/description/{abstract:$9}",
      "/data/@/data/child_collections/@/@/{name:$10, uri:$11}",
    ]
    , "dest":target_elvis_ltc
  }
  , "orcid_person_data":{
    "src":[
      "/person/name/given-names/{value:$1}",
      "/person/name/family-name/{value:$2}",
      "/person/emails/email/@/{email:$3}",
      "/person/keywords/keyword/@/{content:$4}",
      "/activities-summary/employments/affiliation-group/@/summaries/@/employment-summary/{department-name:$5}",
      "/activities-summary/employments/affiliation-group/@/summaries/@/employment-summary/{role-title:$6}",
      "/history/last-modified-date/{value:$7}",
    ]
    , "dest": target_orcid_person_data
  }
}
```

Figure 7: Capture of variables, in JSON dict paths (\$ variables) during parsing in order transform the output to other structures (Latimer Core for ELViS) and read the input of other APIs (eg. ORCID)

2. Get institutions by identifiers (note the possibility to change the protocols) :
 - i. https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/institutions/?operation=get_by_id&protocol=ror&values=02v6zg374
 - ii. https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/institutions/?operation=get_by_id&protocol=grscicoll&values=LMOB
 - iii. https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/institutions/?operation=get_by_id&protocol=index_herbarium&values=L
 - iv. Parameter has path via .htaccess or rewriterule for shortened URLs :<https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf/api/institutions/ror/02v6zg374>
3. Fuzzy query (institutions):
 - i. https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/institutions/?operation=query_str&q=wien

The protocol for the main identifiers is the CETAF one, with the ISO code of the country as 1st level identifier and the acronym as second level identifier, e.g.:

- BE-RBINS
- BE-RMCA
- ES-CEAB-CSIC
- DE-MFN
- FR-MNHN

```

{
  "pager": {
    "page": 1,
    "page_size": 58,
    "size": 58
  },
  "data": [
    {
      "uuid": "11b2310a-cace-4c2b-baaa-6b965959ea31",
      "uuid_institution_normalized": "12ac3274-0f80-4fe2-93aa-5232fe69337f",
      "current": true,
      "version": 1,
      "identifier": "AT-BC Upper Austrian State Museum - Biology Centre",
      "data": {
        "data_list": [
          {
            "data": {
              "count": 1,
              "limit": 20,
              "offset": 0,
              "results": [
                {
                  "address": [
                    {
                      "postalCode": "4020",
                      "addressType": "Physical",
                      "addressRegion": "Upper Austria",
                      "streetAddress": "Museumstra\u00dfe 14",
                      "addressCountry": "AT",
                      "addressLocality": "Linz"
                    },
                    {
                      "postalCode": "4020",
                      "addressType": "Mailing",
                      "addressRegion": "Upper Austria",
                      "streetAddress": "Museumstra\u00dfe 14",
                      "addressCountry": "AT",
                      "addressLocality": "Linz"
                    }
                  ]
                }
              ]
            }
          }
        ]
      }
    }
  ],
  "reference": {

```

Figure 9: Example of output (list operation) of the Django backend for institutions.

Collections

The collection information is divided in 3 forms:

- General Overview with general information about the collections of an institution
- Collection with detailed information about a (sub-)discipline
- Collection digitisation of a discipline and subdisciplines

The General Overview form aims to collect information about the diversity of the collections of an institution. The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, of the Institution and about the collections
- Collections description
- Form completion

Figure 10: Data model of the General Overview of collections form.

The collection form aims to collect information about a specific discipline or subdiscipline following the hierarchy of collections.

The identification of a collection is achieved using a persistent identifier(s) based on the following sequence: ISO Country - Institution Acronym - DiSSCo Discipline - DiSSCo sub-discipline - Collection name.

The identifier corresponding to the collection of the human remains from Spy cave is BE-RBINS-ANT-BIO-SpyCave.

The hierarchy is based on the One World Collection division (Johnson and Owens, 2023) and the Synthesys+ Collections dashboard (Tiley et al., 2024) and adapted to fit the requirements of the DiSSCo infrastructure. This hierarchy of the collections into disciplines

and subdisciplines was created during the Collection Dashboard exercise (Synthesis + project, DiSSCo prepare and Transition project).

Eleven disciplines were defined (Figure 11):

1. Algae, Fungi, Plants (old Botany)
2. Invertebrates Zoology
3. Vertebrates Zoology
4. Anthropology
5. Palaeontology
6. Geology
7. Astrogeology
8. Environmental DNA
9. Microbiology
10. Heritage
11. Data

Disciplines forms

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Figure 11: The eleven disciplines covered.

Each discipline is divided into several sub-disciplines including the unspecified and other categories. A total of 74 sub-disciplines are therefore identified in the hierarchy following the DiSSCo hierarchy.

Figure 12: Hierarchy of information and associated form featuring, for RBINS: One institution, eleven disciplines, and seventy-four subdisciplines.

Each discipline and subdiscipline is identified using abbreviation (Figure 13) composed by the 3 first letters e.g. ANT for Anthropology or the first letters of the components e.g. LGS for Liquid Gas Samples.

Country	BE											
Institution	RBINS											
ISO	BE											
Institution	RBINS											
Discipline	AFP	INV	VER	ANT	PAL	GEO	AST	ECO	MIC	HER	DAT	
Subdiscipline	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	SPA	NS	PHA	NS	NS	
Subdiscipline	ALG	INS	FIS	BIO	AFP	MIN	MET		BAC	DOC	MEA	
Subdiscipline	FUN	ARA	AMP	ARC	INV	PET	TEC		PLA	LIB	OBS	
Subdiscipline	BRY	CRU	REP		VER	SED			PRO	SOU	DIB	
Subdiscipline	PTE	MOL	BIR			SOI			EUK	MOD	DIG	
Subdiscipline	SEE	POR	MAM			ICE			VIR		MET	
Subdiscipline		CNI				LGS			YEA			
Subdiscipline		ECH				MSS			ALG			
Genetic Ressources	PGR	IGR	VGR	AGR					DNA			
Other	OTH											
	74	8	10	8	5	5	9	4	3	9	6	7

Figure 13: Abbreviations used to define the disciplines and subdisciplines.

The use of this classification allows to include the collections in a specialisation exercise using a standardised hierarchy. We created a template which allows us to create all disciplines and subdisciplines codes for an institution according to the hierarchy proposed by DiSSCo and CETAF.

The template to create such identification codes is available at the following address: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1-kb0PIoRFJA8Y5Wnf-coEiREy0LP9jTLN-4M0Y4HmE8/edit?usp=sharing>

The collection form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, of the Institution and about the collections
- Collections description
- Form completion

Figure 14: Data model of the collection form.

The Digitisation form aims to collect information about the digitisation of the collection for a specific discipline. The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person and the institution
- Digitisation description including CMS, DAMS, imaging workflow(s), metadata and statistics
- Form completion

The protocol for the main identifiers of the collections is the CETAF one, e.g:

- BE-RBINS GEO (Geology of the RBINS)
- BE-RBINS GEO-MIN (subcollection mineralogy)
- ES-EBD-CSIC AFP
- ES-EBD-CSIC AFP-ALG

Data is read from several Excel sheets (for thematic: taxonomy, conservation, locations) uploaded in the Google cloud from the form, with the parent collection in the first column and subcollections on other columns).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	AFRICA	Geology unspecified (GEO)	Minerals and Gems (GEO-MIN)	Petrology (GEO-PET)	Sediments (GEO-SED)	Soils (GEO-SOI)	Water-ice (GEO-ICE)	Liquid or gaseous (GEO-LGS)	Mixed Geology (GEO-MSS)	Geology Other (GEO-OTH)	
2	DZ - Algeria	Yes	Yes	Yes							
3	AO - Angola	Yes	Yes	Yes							
4	SH - Ascension	Yes									
5	BJ - Benin										
6	BW - Botswana	Yes	Yes	Yes							
7	BF - Burkina Faso	Yes	Yes	Yes							
8	BI - Burundi	Yes	Yes	Yes							
9	CM - Cameroon	Yes	Yes	Yes							
0	CV - Cape Verde Islands		Yes								

Figure 15: Example of attached detailed form for collections.

```

    },
    "source": "orcid"
  }
},
"collection_data": {
  "storage": {
    "dried_not_assembled": {
      "object_quantity": {
        "detail": {
          "SOILS": 0,
          "PETROLOGY": 25000,
          "SEDIMENTS": 428000,
          "WATER-ICE": 0,
          "GEOLOGY-OTHER": 0,
          "MIXED-GEOLOGY": 0,
          "LIQUID-OR-GASEOUS": 0,
          "MINERALS-AND-GEMS": 35000
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "geospatial_coverage": {
    "country_list": {
      "Asia": {
        "IQ - Iraq": {
          "PETROLOGY": "Yes",
          "MINERALS-AND-GEMS": "Yes"
        },
        "IR - Iran": {
          "PETROLOGY": "Yes",
          "MINERALS-AND-GEMS": "Yes"
        },
        "LA - Laos": {
          "PETROLOGY": "Yes",
          "MINERALS-AND-GEMS": "Yes"
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 16: Overview of collection data in the API.

Once parsed, the data are available through the following API endpoints:

1. List of collections :
https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/collections/?operation=list&size=100
2. Collections by collection identifier (as for institution, different protocols are possible; CETAF, ROR, GRSciColl) :
https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/collections/?operation=get_by_id&protocol=cetaf&values=BE-RBINS%20GEO

Data can also be transformed into alternative output formats, predefined in the settings of the Django environment (see above), by using the *transform* parameter. Example with Latimer Core for ELViS :

https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/collections/?operation=get_by_id&protocol=cetaf&values=BE-RBINS%20GEO&transform=elvis_ltc


```

{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "ror",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "02y22ws83"
},
{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "cetaf_complete",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "BE-RBINS Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences"
},
{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "cetaf",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "BE-RBINS"
}
],
"ltc:MeasurementOrFact": [
  {
    "dwc:measurementType": "collection_type",
    "ltc:measurementFactText": "main_collection"
  },
  {
    "dwc:measurementType": "count_objects",
    "dwc:measurementValue": 488000
  },
  {
    "dwc:measurementType": "count_types",
    "dwc:measurementValue": 17
  }
],
"ltc:GeographicContext": [
  {
    "ltc:region": "South America",
    "dwc:countryCode": "AR",
    "dwc:country": "Argentina"
  },
  {
    "ltc:region": "South America",
    "dwc:countryCode": "BO",
    "dwc:country": "Bolivia"
  },
  {
    "ltc:region": "South America",
    "dwc:countryCode": "BR",
    "dwc:country": "Brazil"
  },
  {
    "ltc:region": "South America",
    "dwc:countryCode": "CL",
    "dwc:country": "Chile"
  }
]

```

Figure 17: Latimer Core representation of a collection (through API)

	B	C	D	
group	Field	parent path	definition	is_a
1	ltc:identifier	ltc:hasParentOrganisationalUnit\ltc:identifier	list_of the identifiers of the parent institution	y
1.1	ltc:identifier\ltc:identifierSource	ltc:hasParentOrganisationalUnit\ltc:identifier	protocol of the identifier	n
1.2	ltc:identifier\ltc:identifierValue	ltc:hasParentOrganisationalUnit\ltc:identifier	value of the identifier	n
2	ltc:MeasurementOrFact			
2.1	ltc:MeasurementOrFact\dwc:measurementType		type of measurement	y
2.2	ltc:MeasurementOrFact\measurementFactText		value (text)	n
or				
2.2	ltc:MeasurementOrFact\dwc:measurementValue		value (numeric)	n
3	ltc:GeographicContext			y
3.1	ltc:GeographicContext\ltc:region		Geographic area (based on TDWG categories)	
3.2	ltc:GeographicContext\countryCode		ISO 3166 2 letters	
3.3	ltc:GeographicContext\country		country name	
4	ltc:Person		coordinates of the curator (data come from ORCID)	
4.1	ltc:Person\hasRole			
4.2	ltc:Person\fullName			
4.3	ltc:Person\hasIdentifier		ORCID identifier	
4.4.1	ltc:Person\ltc:hasContactDetail\identifierType		mail (field qualifier)	

Figure 18: List of Latimer Core terms used for collection

Facilities

The Facility form (Figure 19) aims to collect information about a specific facility and associated instruments. The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person and the institution
- Facility description including description, associated instruments, service, practical information
- Form completion

The Instruments XLS file (Figure 20) aims to collect information about the associated instruments.

The XLS file is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, the institution and the instrument
- Instrument section including description, software, service and practical information
- Form completion

Figure 19: Data model of the Facility Form.

Figure 20: Data model of the instruments XLS sheet.

Research

The Research field form (Figure 21) aims to collect information about the research of an institution. Each research field defined by the research model strategy has to be encoded as a separate form.

The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, the institution and the research field
- Research field description including research subject, related collections, research strategy
- Form completion

Figure 21: Data model of the Research field form.

Expertise

The expertise form (Figure 22) aims to collect information about expertise of an institution. Each expertise has to be encoded as a separate form. The individual expertise is not the purpose as it is already developed by the TETTRIs Expertise tool.

The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, the institution and the expertise
- Expertise Description including category, technical discipline, description, publication Related collections, Geography, Stratigraphy, Practical information
- Form completion

Figure 22: Data model of the Expertise form.

Museum

The Specialisation Tool has 2 forms dedicated to the Galleries, displaying collections of the institutions (Figure 23) and the Temporary exhibition (Figure 24) which demonstrates the capacity of the institution to produce exhibition(s) in the framework of touring exhibition and/or co-production.

Each gallery corresponds to one form submission. Each temporary exhibition developed by the institution corresponds to one form submission.

There could therefore be several forms for one institution.

The Gallery form aims to collect information about each gallery (permanent exhibition). The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, the institution and the gallery
- Description including description, related collections, practical informations
- Form completion

Figure 23: Data model of the Gallery form.

The Exhibition form aims to collect information about each temporary exhibition developed by the institution. The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, the institution and the exhibition
- Description including description, related collections, practical informations
- Form completion

Figure 24: Data model of the Temporary Exhibition form.

Training

The training form (Figure 25) aims to collect information about the existing training capacity of the CETAF/DiSSCo members to see how these can be shared or proposed as service.

The form is divided in 3 parts:

- Identification of the contact person, of the Institution and about the training
- training description
- Form completion

Figure 25: Data model of the Training form.

2.3. Data Collection workflow

The workflow is composed of several steps allowing the manual input (1) and/or the API input avoiding the multiple encoding (2). The data are aggregated in an intermediate database (3) and exported in a central index in ElasticSearch (5).

The Django API is also the connector with DiSSCo / ELViS and GBIF / GRSciColl (4) while the ElasticSearch API is used by the CETAF website (6).

The update of the information is proposed to the institutions using pre-filled forms (1) based on the Elastic Search index (tested) or the Django API (7).

Steps:

- 1) Collect with Google Forms and Google Sheets with manual input of ROR ID, ORCID ID and GRSciColl ID. Linkage between the Google forms and sheets and the API is done via Python libraries, using OAuth 2.0 access tokens to copy content of documents stored in Google cloud documents into Python objects from the “Pandas” library. Content of Google sheets are then converted into JSON (via Pandas) and stored in an intermediate database table, acting as a cache. This avoids querying the Google cloud each time the same data needs to be re-harvested and parsed for conversion into a modified output structure;
- 2) Collect using Django API of the data from;

- ROR
 - ORCID
 - GRSciColl (+ Index Herbarium)
- 3) Intermediate database PostgreSQL;
 - 4) Export data to ELViS/DiSSCo and GRSciColl and data update (Django API);
 - 5) ElasticSearch Indexes;
 - 6) Export data to CETAF website (Elastic API);
 - 7) Prefilled forms for update using ElasticSearch Index (tested) or Django API (to develop with validation workflow of the automatically gathered data).

2.4. Maintenance and development responsibility

The development of the Specialisation Tool has been done through a partnership between the RBINS and the CETAF Secretariat. Franck Theeten (RMCA/RBINS) and Patrick Semal (RBINS) have developed the Specialisation Tool back-end and front-end. The CETAF Secretariat has helped to steer the strategic vision and provide practical input based on community and DiSSCo infrastructure needs.

Once the CETAF registry platform is developed the next step will be to have it fully hosted on the CETAF servers where the CETAF Secretariat will be solely responsible for maintenance of all its components.

2.5. Sustainability and maintenance

The Specialisation Tool is currently hosted at the RMCA, Belgium. During this development phase, the technical components, including the PostgreSQL database, Django API, and Grafana dashboards, are maintained on RMCA servers. Once the platform reaches its full operational maturity, hosting and maintenance responsibilities will be permanently transferred to CETAF.

CETAF will assume long-term responsibility for ensuring the stability, security, and continuity of the Specialisation Tool. This includes maintaining the technical infrastructure, regularly updating and upgrading the software environment, and ensuring that all data is securely backed up. It is foreseen that data backups, including the PostgreSQL database, will be performed on a regular basis, with options for yearly long-term preservation through certified services such as those developed by Belgian federal scientific institutions.

In addition, RBINS will continue collaborating with CETAF on the future development and enhancement of both the front-end and back-end components, ensuring that the platform remains aligned with evolving user needs and technical standards.

CETAF will also coordinate the regular updating of institutional data. To maintain data accuracy and relevance, CETAF will disseminate pre-filled forms to participating institutions on a six-monthly to yearly basis. These pre-filled forms will allow institutions

to review, validate, and update their information efficiently, helping to ensure that the Specialisation Tool remains a reliable and up-to-date resource for the broader natural science collections community.

The data will be open access, in line with DiSSCo's Access and Data Policies and the FAIR principles, and openly accessible to all users, subject to appropriate attribution.

3. Exploitation roadmap

This section provides the detailed plan for completion of the CETAF-DiSSCo Specialisation Tool.

3.1. Linkage to DiSSCo services

European Loans and Visits service (ELViS)

Service description: [ELViS](#) is a one-stop access point to NSCs in Europe. It provides a unified way to request visits, loans and virtual access to the collections. Virtual access requests through ELViS introduce a new type of access: digitisation on demand. Furthermore, the request mechanism implemented in ELViS also enables future services for tracking usage metrics, monitoring and reporting and connecting collection usage with research outputs.

Service development status (In the development process): Operational

Data needs:

- the contact coordinates of an institution
- the contact coordinates of the scientific curator
- the list of facilities attached to the collection
- the address of an institution
- the terms of use and condition of access to a collections
- the loan policy of an institution

Linkage to the Specialisation Tool: ELViS will connect the CETAF collection API, though the Latimer Core endpoint (e.g.

https://naturalheritage.africamuseum.be/cetaf_survey_api/collections/?operation=get_by_id&protocol=cetaf&values=BE-RBINS%20GEO&transform=elvis_ltc). The Latimer Core profile elaborated by ELViS ([ELViS/LtC profile ELViS at review · Maxime-Griveau/ELViS · GitHub](#)) also helped defining the Latimer Core profile of the CETAF API.


```

{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "index_herbarium",
  "ltc:identifierValue": ""
},
{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "grid",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "grid.20478.39"
},
{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "ror",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "02y22ws83"
},
{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "cetaf_complete",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "BE-RBINS Royal Belgian Institute of
atural Sciences"
},
{
  "ltc:identifierSource": "cetaf",
  "ltc:identifierValue": "BE-RBINS"
}
]
},
"Collections": [
{
  "ltc:organisationalUnit": {
    "ltc:organisationUnitType": "Collection",
    "ltc:identifier": [
      "BE-RBINS GEO"
    ],
    "ltc:description": [
      "The rich geological collection contains rocks, minerals
nd meteorites, as well as drill cores and descriptions of
rillings. 400,000 samples of Belgian soil, 40km of drill cores,
5,000+minerals and 1,900+ meteorites."
    ]
  }
}
]
}

```

Figure 26: Transformation of the output into Latimer Core data (for linking with ELViS).

Collection Digitisation Dashboard (CDD)

Service description: The aim of the [CDD](#) is to provide a dynamic window for stakeholders to discover the contents, coverage and strengths of European Natural Science Collections (both digitised and undigitised), as well as a tool for digitisation prioritisation, measuring digitisation progress and high-level decision making.

Service development status (In the development process): Pilot implementation from SYNTHESYS+, there is no information on

Linkage to the Specialisation Tool: The CDD was developed by the NHM, London in the framework of the Synthesys+ project. It used the data collected by the Collections Dashboard created by Laura Tilley (CETAF) during the same EU project (Tilley *et al.*, 2024).

The CDD uses Microsoft Power BI. The first view (Figure 27) displays information about the institutions, the estimated total number of specimens and the number of digitised specimens according to the MIDS values.

Figure 27: First view of the CDD.

The second view (Figure 28) displays information about the diversity of the collections including the taxonomy, the preservation and the stratigraphy for the paleontological specimens.

Figure 28: Second view of the CDD.

Finally, the third view (Figure 29) allows selectors (institutions, discipline, digitisation level, preservation method, taxonomy and characteristics) to prepare detailed views.

Figure 29: Third view of the CDD.

The CDD is presently used by DiSSCo-UK and by DiSSCo Flanders. For both, it was included in GBIF hosted portals exposing the subset of GBIF data corresponding to the institutions of the two consortia but CDD is not proposed as a DiSSCo service for all NN.

CETAF and RBINS explored how the Power BI dashboard can be extended to the other Specialisation Tool sections. MBG (Maarten Trekels) provided the Power BI files of DiSSCo Flanders network. The online version of the Power BI included in the MS Office 365 licence does not allow updating the source data. The desktop version (only Windows) allows the update but the produced dashboards are only visible by users with a MS Office 365 licence and are not visible by any user. The proposed licence allowing public interactive dashboards has a cost of 800€/month without taxes. This is too expensive for a long term service at the CETAF level.

We propose to use the Grafana Open Source solution. This visualisation tool collects, correlates and visualises data with dashboards. It could be connected directly to a PostgreSQL database allowing instant update of the dashboards with a completely automatic update of the data. (<https://github.com/grafana/grafana?pg=oss-graf&plcmt=hero-btn-3>). See also section 3.3.

DiSSCover

Service description: [DiSSCover](#) will provide event-based curation and annotation functions on the DS for experts in the community and for machines. Transactions on the data will be stored as well as provenance information related to the curation or annotation events.

Service development status (In the development process): Pilot/Sandbox stage.

Data needs: DiSSCover to incorporate the collection of unique PIDs used in the Specialisation Tool.

Linkage to the specialisation tool: Since DiSSCover operates at the specimen level and the specialisation tool at the collection level, it is envisioned that each DiSSCover specimen will be linked to a resolvable collection PID/URL, directing users to the corresponding specialisation tool for the collection that the specimen belongs to.

3.2. Data pipelines with external data portals

Aside from ELViS (Section 3.1), the API provides data to GRSciColl, the registry of natural sciences institutions and collections managed by the GBIF (<https://scientific-collections.gbif.org/>).

Figure 30. Binding the API to GRSciColl.

GRSciColl will request data from the API, using the Latimer Core endpoint, when users register collections to GRSciColl by providing their CETAF identifier among a list of several other possible identifiers also offered by GrSiColl, such as Index Herbarium, GRID. Specific collections will then be pulled from the API, using the URL with the CETAF identifier as a HTTP GET parameter. There will be no batch harvesting, to enhance quality control on data and limit the risk of loops (GRSciColl harvesting data of the CETAF API that come from itself). The workflow will only concern the parent collections (first level identifiers such as INV, VER, GEO), while subcollections will be provided as a nested list using the Latimer Core ObjectClassification group. GRSciColl is interested in data on the geographic coverage and physical storage/conservation information, along with their MIDS identifiers.

3.3. Data presentation and Visualisation enhancement

The CETAF/DiSSCo Specialisation Tool is envisioned to be integrated into the [CETAF website](#), which already features a user-friendly interface suited for presenting and

exploring information. This section outlines interface design concepts that were conceived during the DiSSCo Transition Project but could not be implemented due to time and resource constraints. These ideas will continue to be developed beyond the project's timeframe.

The CETAF website is built on the WordPress Content Management System (CMS). The plan is to reorganize the website's structure to better support access to services such as the Specialisation Tool. This will also enable seamless integration with other key components, including the Plone system—where DiSSCo and CETAF members can access data provider forms—and the CDD, which allows users to search institutional collections.

The following paragraphs present the proposed design ideas for integrating the Specialisation Tool into the CETAF website.

Specialisation Tool homepage

Access to the tool will be available through the website's main menu (See Figure 31). The current menu item “Explore” will be renamed to “Tools.” When users select “Tools,” a dropdown will appear offering access to the “Specialisation ToolPlan,” which expands into a third navigation layer with options for:

- Institution Data
- Collection Data
- Research Expertise
- Training and Facilities

Selecting “Specialisation Tool” from the dropdown menu will lead to the tool's main landing page. Figure 32 shows a basic mock-up of the proposed layout.

Figure 31: Screenshot of the CETAF Website current navigation menu, highlighting how a user would be able to access the Specialisation Tool. The yellow speech bubble at the top presents the

proposal for changing part of the current navigation bar to better accommodate the Specialisation Tool.

Figure 32: Simple mock-up (low-Fi) design proposal for the arrangement of elements on the Specialisation Tool home page.

Institution page

Clicking the “Institution” button on the Specialisation Tool page will direct users to the institution search page (Figure 33). Figure 33 shows the institution search page that is currently seen in the CETAF website, it has a search menu and a table presents the institution name, country, contact, representatives, and whether they are a member of CETAF and/or DiSSCo. We propose some slight alterations to the page as highlighted in Figure 33. On the current institution page, users can click an orange “Info” button next to any listed institution to view more detailed information about that institution. This leads to a dedicated institution profile page, with proposed updates illustrated in Figures 34 and 35.

The sections for facilities, research expertise, and training will also be presented in a layout similar to the institution pages, maintaining a consistent and user-friendly design across the Specialisation Tool. However, these pages are still under development and will be finalised once the specific data fields and structures to be collected are fully agreed upon.

Explore Taxonomic Institutions

[HOME](#) / [Explore](#) / Explore our Institutions

This database allows you to explore the facilities and resources of CETAF member institutions and beyond. There are more than 150 sources of data in here. From the type and size of collections to laboratories, staff and research areas, with these institutional profiles you can discover up-to-date information about Europe's museums, botanic gardens and research centres.

For example, these lists from about 100 different institutions. The institutional profiles will help you obtain that information and get in touch with the data experts. Collectively, our institutional profiles provide an overview of European collectors. Looking for the opportunity to exchange seed samples, for example? The search tools let you filter by research topic, specific collections or key tools, to find the exact institution to meet your needs.

ABOUT US • COMMUNITY • **EXPLORE** • ONGOING • RESOURCES • LATEST • MY PROFILE

Search

Search By Institutions

Filters

Select Country

Select Research Field **To change Institution type**

Select Membership

Show 10 entries

Global search

Remove column

Institution Name	Country	Contact	Representative	Research Fields	Membership	More Infos
AT-BC Upper Austrian State Museum - Biology Centre	AT - Austria	bio-linz@ooe-lk.at	Mr. Prof. Dr. Alfred Weidinger	Archaeology Anthropology Geological Biological		Infos
AT-NHMW Natural History Museum, Vienna	AT - Austria	info@nhm-wien.ac.at	. Katrin Vohland			Infos
BE-MBG Meise Botanic Garden	BE - Belgium	info@plantentuinmeise.be	Dr. Steven Dessenin	Algae, Fungi, Plants (Old Botany) Palaeontology Ecology Taxonomy	 	Infos
BE-RBINS Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences	BE - Belgium	info@naturalsciences.be	Mr. Michel Van Camp	Biological Zoology Taxonomy MolecularBiology (and more...)	 	Infos
BG-NMNH-SBAS National Museum of Natural History Sofia	BG - Bulgaria	contact@nmnhs.com	Prof. Dr. Pavel Stoev	AnthropologyBiological Taxonomy Mineralogy/Petrology Paleontology	 	Infos
CH-MHNG Natural History Museum of Geneva	CH - Switzerland	info.museum@geneve.ch	Dr. Arnaud Maeder			Infos
DE-MFN Berlin Natural History Museum	DE - Germany	info@mfn-berlin.de	Prof. Johannes Vogel	Biological Geological		Infos
DE-SMNS Stuttgart State Museum of Natural History	DE - Germany	museum@smns.de	Prof. Dr. Lars Krogmann			Infos
DE-SNSB Bavarian Natural History Collections	DE - Germany	generalsekretariat@snsb.de	Prof. Dr. Joris Peters		 	Infos
DK-SNM-KU Natural History Museum of Denmark	DK - Denmark	snm@snm.ku.dk	Prof. Nina Rønsted			Infos

Showing 1 to 10 of 56 entries

Previous **1** 2 3 4 5 6 Next

Phone
+32 (0)2 627 42 51
+32 (0)2 627 42 50
+32 (0)2 627 42 30

Mail
info@di.org

Address
c/o Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
Rue Vautier, 29
B-1000 - Brussels
Belgium

Social

Legal
[Privacy Policy](#)
[Institution infos](#)

Sitemap
[About Us](#)
[Community](#)
[Explore](#)
[Activities](#)
[Resources](#)
[News](#)
[My Profile](#)

Subscribe to e.pulse, the electronic Newsletter of the European Taxonomic Community

E-mail address compulsory field

Figure 33: Screenshot of the Institution page of the Specialisation Tool. The yellow speech boxes present proposed changes.

Figure 34: Screenshot and part mock-up of an individual institution details page. It presents the institution's name and an accordion menu, the white boxes with Add is, these represent the additional needed accordion boxes.

Figure 35: Screenshot and partial mock-up of the institution detail page, but showing an example of the layout of information for the accordion box “Institution info” when it is expanded.

Figure 36: Screenshot and partial mock-up of the current collection page but here we have added the image of the SYNTHESYS+ Collection Dashboard.

After evaluation of the Power BI tool use by NHM for the Collection digitisation dashboards

Grafana (open-source solution in Go) has been tested as a dashboard tool to visualise the assessment data. A test connection has been made with data coming from DISSCoFlanders, kindly provided by the project manager. Linking to the survey data has yet to be done, but could be easily implemented by connecting SQL views once the data structure is stable and validated.

Test URL: <https://naturalheritage.africanmuseum.be/grafana/goto/ncN-NwJNg?orgId=1>

Figure 36: Example of collection data visualised in a Grafana dashboard (with data coming from DISSCO Flanders. Note the two hierarchically dependent variable selectors at the top left (geographical ecological region and institutions).

Figure 37: Example of collection data visualised in a Grafana dashboard (with data coming from actual survey : here the list of CETAF institutions containing object and data from Senegal).

On a technical level, the binding between the API and Grafana is made by *ad hoc* SQL views in the PostgreSQL database that aggregate and re-normalize the data in JSON, by using the query fields (e.g continent, country and hosting institutions) as pseudo primary keys, and counting distinct (e.g number of collections) entries and/or performing a sum on numeric indicators (e.g total number of specimens or type specimens). Views are then queried in each visualisation defined in a Grafana dashboard panel.

3.4. Engagement strategy

Audience

The DiSSCo Specialisation Tool is primarily designed to collect the data from NSCs from the DiSSCo Community in order to make them accessible to a diverse range of users within

the DiSSCo RI and the CETAF network. The platform centralises the collections of partner institutions, and enables users to extract and highlight essential information on these NSCs data.

The target audience of this tool includes:

- Users seeking digital and non-digital resources and expertise related to NSCs.
- The DiSSCo management team, which collects and displays information on collections from partner institutions to enhance their visibility and accessibility.

More specifically, the tool is particularly valuable for:

- Researchers in natural sciences, who can use it to locate and analyse relevant collections for their studies.
- Digitisation process managers, responsible for overseeing the (standardised) digitization process of collections.
- Curators and collection managers, who contribute with specimens data and manage collection records within the infrastructure.
- Institutional management staff, ensuring the alignment of their collections with DiSSCo's objectives and policies.
- Data providers and users, facilitating the integration and use of standardised collection data.
- Policy makers, looking for tangible data on the National and European strengths and expertise in , physical and digitised , distributed and reliable European natural science collections supporting decision making.

Added value of the tool for the users

The DiSSCo Specialisation Tool offers significant added value to users by serving as a centralised platform for gathering, categorising, storing, and analysing expertise related to NSCs. By integrating knowledge from various institutions, the tool enhances the discoverability of expertise and assets across the DiSSCo RI network.

As a powerful search engine, the tool enables users to navigate institutional assets and expertise efficiently, providing a strategic overview of available collections, facilities, training opportunities, and scientific infrastructures. As a decision-support tool, it helps identify gaps in the network and informs management strategies to optimise DiSSCo's capacity deployment.

With its dedicated management and visualisation dashboards, facilitate fast and efficient analysis of multidisciplinary NSC-related data for varied stakeholders, including government bodies, institutions, and researchers requiring focused and relevant data in support of evidence-based decision-making.

Centres of Excellence : Thanks to the richness of the DiSSCo NSCs, research community the tool enables the localisation and access to Centres of Excellence (CoEs) and their specificities based on predefined criteria (Highlighted in Annex 2). It allows users to

analyse key NSC-related data, such as the number of specimens per collection type, the extent of digitisation, curatorial expertise, research fields, and scientific instruments used. Institutions can inform on their collections dedicated to exhibitions and their training programmes for collection curation and digitisation techniques.

By improving the visibility and accessibility of European NSCs, the DiSSCo Specialisation Tool empowers a wide range of users to make informed decisions, support collaboration, and strengthen the overall DiSSCo RI.

Promotion and key messages

The DiSSCo community and notably its NN are the drivers populating the Specialisation tool. On several occasions, and notably NN meetings, the team working on the development and data gathering of the tool have presented the tool components, back-end and front end and final outcomes and potential. Today, 69 institutions from 16 countries have populated the platform with their data and more countries are regularly encouraged to contribute to this effort which will benefit the whole community. By adhering to this common endeavour, each institution highlights its uniqueness and adds value to the community. By filling in with some of its data the Specialisation Tool, the institutions enable it to provide a comprehensive overview of the assets distributed across the DiSSCo RI network, offering seamless access to data from over 100 institutions of natural sciences. This tool enhances collaboration by fostering direct exchanges between researchers, collection managers, and curators, strengthening the connection between users and collections.

Designed to align with the FAIR principles, the tool ensures accessibility, harmonisation, and standardisation of European NSCs. It integrates standardised and classified data and metadata, supported by clear PIDs. Additionally, it enables the visualisation and sharing of multimedia files associated with digital specimens within the DiSSCo infrastructure, including high-resolution images, Computed Tomography (CT), micro-CT scans, 3D models, and uncompressed sound files.

By centralising access to invaluable digital specimens and facilitating standardised data sharing, the DiSSCo Specialisation Tool plays a crucial role in advancing natural sciences research across Europe.

The two above-mentioned services (the PostgreSQL/DJANGO API, developed specifically for the project and the Grafana dashboard) are currently hosted on a server at the Royal Museum for Central Africa / Africamuseum in Tervuren, and still in the development phase. Once ready for production, they will be moved to the CETAF server, on the *cetaf.org* Internet domain, to reflect their European audience and ease technical linking with the CETAF website, as well as the database management and update of data. As they are based on open-source tools, the transfer will not involve licence costs. We recommend running them on two separate Docker containers, or (preferably) images on virtual machines (to ease separated backup of each of them, in a single image file). The server should have a physical RAID-5 device. The PostgreSQL database could be sent to a LTP

(Long Term Preservation) storage service on a yearly basis, such as the platform of the Belgian scientific institution developed by the Smals ([SMALS](#)).

The initial acquisition of data is based on services provided by Google (Google Forms and Google sheets). While being technically flexible and cheap to implement, this solution is not optimal in terms of technical stability and security. It also raises issues in terms of GDPR and data ownership. The linkage and transfer of data between the API and the Google cloud document is made through OAuth 2.0, which is quite complex to implement and raises security concerns, as connection credentials need to be stored on the server, and exposed to the Python context of the Django context from static files). The Django framework could also be used to replace the Google forms by webpages, with access rights stored in the same database, to improve robustness and self-integration of the workflow and limit technical dependency to services provided by an external company.

3.5. Access and usage monitoring by the service provider

The DiSSCo Specialisation Tool will be available as an e-service hosted on the CETAF [website](#) (see section 3.3), with a centralised access point integrated into the DiSSCo portal.

As a virtual service, the Specialisation Tool is accessible via Wide Virtual Access, allowing users to interact with the tool remotely and efficiently. Access to the service is provided free of charge at the point of use. However, in exceptional cases, value-added services may be offered on a cost-recovery basis, as specified in the DiSSCo RI Services Catalogue.

Prior to gaining access, users must comply with DiSSCo's Access Policy, Data Policy, and Intellectual Property Rights Policy. They are also expected to endorse DiSSCo's commitment to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles, and to actively support data reuse and transparency in the context of their engagement with DiSSCo-provided resources.

User support for accessing and using the Specialisation Tool is provided through DiSSCo's [Helpdesk](#) and the documentation available in the DiSSCo [Knowledge Base](#). Access to the service may require users to log in or demonstrate an affiliation with an institution that is part of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure. Detailed procedures for accessing and using the tool are outlined in the DiSSCo [Services Catalogue](#).

Access to the Specialisation Tool may be suspended for administrative, operational, or security reasons. In such cases, users will receive a minimum of one week's notice, without entitlement to compensation. Immediate suspension may occur if a user fails to adhere to the applicable use policies, including DiSSCo's Data Policy and service-specific terms.

The DiSSCo Hub/ and /or CETAF as the Specialisation Tool long-term management team, will monitor and evaluate usage and impact of the Specialisation Tool in accordance with DiSSCo's Access Policy. All monitoring and assessment activities will be conducted in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) where personal data is involved.

3.6. User support

To ensure a seamless user experience, the DiSSCo Specialisation Tool is supported by a comprehensive user assistance framework, including the DiSSCo and CETAF help desks, detailed user manuals, video tutorials, and webinars. These resources help users to effectively engage with the tool, navigate its features, and integrate their data efficiently.

As part of this effort, dedicated webinar sessions have already been conducted by the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences within the framework of Be.DiSSCo-Fed, the Belgian Federal initiative to align the digitization of the Belgian collections with DiSSCo RI. During these sessions, the tool's developers guided users from Belgian institutions through the Specialisation Tool, demonstrating its key features, showcasing existing data, and explaining how additional data can be incorporated. This interactive approach highlighted the platform's unique role in centralising and making available the richness of European NSCs.

Participants, including researchers, curators, and data managers, learned how to:

- Navigate the tool's intuitive interface and input collection-related data.
- Explore the standardised descriptions, storage, and visualisation of digitised specimens, including multimedia files.
- Apply best practices for maintaining consistency in data workflows, ensuring interoperability and maximising discoverability.

To further support users, links to already available support platforms are provided in Annex 3, offering direct access to additional guidance and troubleshooting resources.

4. Conclusion

The Specialisation Tool represents a strategic milestone in DiSSCo's development toward a mature, integrated, and service-oriented Research Infrastructure. Designed in close collaboration between RBINS and CETAF, this tool consolidates and streamlines the gathering, structuring, and analysis of high-level institutional and NSCs data across the DiSSCo network. It is built upon a foundation of robust technical design and data workflows, allowing institutions to provide information on their collections, facilities, digitisation capacity, expertise, training, exhibitions, and research.

The Specialisation Tool has already demonstrated its unique value in supporting DiSSCo's broader goals. By enabling a standardised view of the distributed assets of natural science institutions, it lays the groundwork for evidence-based strategic planning, identification of Centres of Excellence, and improved visibility and accessibility of European NSCs. Its hierarchical classification system and persistent identifiers ensure clear traceability and consistent integration across the infrastructure. A major technical achievement is the CETAF API, developed specifically for the project, which has proven functional and effective for institutions and collections. This API is now well integrated with partner services and organisations, including ELViS and GRSciColl. Notably, the project's

collaboration with ELViS helped define a shared Latimer Core-based structure, ensuring data exchange and mutual compatibility. The integration with GRSciColl ensures relevance and discoverability of DiSSCo collections in the global registry of scientific collections. For data visualisation, an Open-Source dashboard solution via Grafana was adopted, enhancing the transparency and usability of the Specialisation Tool.

In addition to support interoperability, the Specialisation Tool strengthens the technical capacity of the DiSSCo consortium, particularly through the implementation of database systems capable of managing diachronic and versioned data. This aspect is crucial for tracking changes and ensuring long-term data consistency across updates. The decision to use Open-Source technologies, such as PostgreSQL and the Django Python framework, has proved highly effective, enabling fast iteration, modular development, and cost-efficiency.

While the initial data collection still relies on Google-based forms and sheets, the core data infrastructure and services are already self-contained and hosted within the DiSSCo ecosystem. Nonetheless, future iterations of the tool may replace the remaining dependencies on external platforms to ensure complete control over data pipelines, reinforce GDPR compliance, and increase technical robustness.

In summary, the Specialisation Tool is a foundational asset for DiSSCo. It enhances the infrastructure's strategic capacity to coordinate and evaluate its network, promotes data harmonisation aligned with FAIR principles, and facilitates the reuse and federation of institutional knowledge across Europe. With its integration into DiSSCo's digital ecosystem, the tool ensures that institutional strengths are not only recognised but also made actionable, setting the stage for a more connected, responsive, and data-driven natural sciences community.

5. References

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6. Annex 1: Glossary

Access: Legitimate and authorised physical, remote and virtual admission to, interactions with and use of Research Infrastructures and to services offered by Research Infrastructures to users.

E-services: Digital resources and tools made available via DiSSCo RI that facilitate virtual access, research and collaboration.

Centres of Excellence: A team with the appropriate leadership and technology, able to transform a natural science collection into digital surrogates of the original specimens. This might be a photograph, a 3D model, or a media asset (e.g. a video) but will always include structured information (metadata) that remains connected to the digital surrogate. A DiSSCo ‘Centre of Excellence’ not only facilitates the process of digitisation but may also manage the lifecycle of these digital objects such as helping to preserve content, protecting the original specimen (especially before and during the digitisation process), improving digital access, and enhancing the return on investment through actions or services on top of the digital surrogate and metadata (Dixey et al., 2020).

DiSSCo Central Hub: The central coordination and support office of DiSSCo ERIC.

DiSSCo Helpdesk: The DiSSCo Helpdesk (<https://dissco.jitbit.com/helpdesk/User/Login>) is a central place for all questions related to DiSSCo services or access programmes such as the virtual access and transnational access calls in ELViS. As such, it is integrated with DiSSCo services. The Helpdesk’s first line support is done by CETAF secretariat while second line support goes to selected CETAF/DiSSCo institutions. Third line support goes to developers of services such as Picturae for ELViS. The Helpdesk is using JitBit software.

DiSSCo Knowledge Base: Knowledge Base - DiSSCo is the dedicated database providing access to outputs from DiSSCo-linked projects (ICEDIG, Synthesys+, and DiSSCo Prepare) that are actively updated.

FAIR principles: Guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Service provider: Organisation or institution, typically a National Node, that offers one or more DiSSCo Services through an agreement with DiSSCo ERIC. Service Provider Agreements define the exact nature of each service and outline the responsibilities of Service Providers, ensuring the delivery of high-quality services in alignment with DiSSCo’s objectives.

User: A person, a team, or an institution from any sector, including public and private sector, making use of data or other services made accessible via DiSSCo RI.

7. Annex 2: Criterion for identification of Centres of Excellence

CoEs can be pinpointed through the tool via identification of existing specialisation among DiSSCo partners.

- Freedom of location: CoE can be based in one physical location or be physically distributed (e.g. a regional network), or virtual.
- Assessment of organisational capabilities: CoE must have the necessary technical, infrastructural, and human capabilities to handle large-scale digitisation projects.
- Standardisation and best practices: CoEs must adhere to standardised digitisation protocols and harmonised practices across thematic, geographic and community boundaries.
- Customisation and flexibility: CoEs must be flexible and open to customisation to meet the specific needs and existing processes of different institutions and to integrate their organisational frameworks into DiSSCo.
- Sustainability and long-term viability: CoEs must have enough financial and operational sustainability to ensure their ability to sustain digitisation efforts over the long term, including the management of ongoing costs and resources.
- Geographical and thematic coverage: CoEs must be geographically distributed in Europe and cover various thematic focuses to ensure a broad and balanced coverage of different regions and scientific themes. CoEs may provide generic digitisation services, and / or have a particular focus (e.g., herbarium sheets, microscope slides, pinned insects), taxonomic groups (e.g. fish, cryptograms, beetles) or geographic and environmental regions (e.g. South America, marine habitats, polar environments).
- Engagement with commercial entities: CoEs can be open to engagement with commercial organisations regarding development and provision of digitisation services.